

Published by:

Center for Integrated Systems Engineering and Advanced Technologies (INTEGRA)
Faculty of Engineering and Built Environment
Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia

The publication date: 31st July 2019

Printed in Bangi, Selangor by Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia — July 2019

Contents

- 1 Vibration Based Energy Harvester
Mohd Faris Farhan A. Fuad, Ramizi Mohamed
- 8 Robot Marin
Muhamad Nizam Ahmad Kamil, Anuar Mikdad Muad
- 14 Pembangunan Kenderaan Kawalan Jauh Bawah Air Beroperasi Permantauan Marin (ROV)
Muhammad Zamir Zainal Abidin, Seri Mastura Mustaza, Iskandar Yahya
- 22 Reka Bentuk, Pemodelan dan Penyelakuan Litar Penyongsang Tersambung Talian Fasa Tunggal
Mohd Muzani Mohamad Saperi, Yushaizad Yusof, Ahmad Asrul Ibrahim
- 29 Investigation Of Solar Hybrid System With Thermoelectric Generator
Muhammad Afiq Mohd Nasir, Ramizi Mohamed, Muhammad Izzam Izmawie Yusoff
- 39 Analisis Audio Berdasarkan Spectrogram dan Scalogram
Nik Salmie Nik Man, Salina Abdul Samad
- 45 Person Re-identification Using Color Based Feature For Surveillance Application
Nigel Tay Tze Hung, Mohamad Hanif Md Saad, Aini Hussain
- 52 Sistem Pemantauan Automatik Hakisan Tanah Pada Tiang Jambatan
Hafifah Ab. Hamid, Anuar Mikdad Muad, Wan Hanna Melini Wan Mohtar
- 58 Child's Age Estimation using Carpal Bones' Characterization
Nurdhiya Zafrah Mat Hassan, Anuar Mikdad Muad
- 64 Simulasi dan Rekabentuk Penukar Kuasa Boost dan Pengesan Titik Kuasa Maksimum bagi Sistem Panel Suria
Mustaffa Kamal Morad, Yushaizad Yusof, Mohd Hairi Mohd Zaman
- 74 Non-small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC) Segmentation on CT Image Using Image Processing
Mohamed Afiq Akmal Mohamed Akil, Siti Salasiah Mokri, Ashrani Aizuddin Abd Rahni, Asraf Mohamed Moubark, Mohd Hairi Mohd Zaman
- 80 The Development of Thermoelectric-Solar Hybrid Energy Harvester System
Muhammad Izzam Izmawie Yusoff, Ramizi Mohamed, Ahmad Asrul Ibrahim

Index of Authors